

Anonymous and Fair Micropayment Scheme with Protection against Coupon Theft

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Abstract

The development of new applications of electronic commerce (e-commerce) that require the payment of small amounts of money to purchase services or goods opens new challenges in the security and privacy fields. This kind of payments is called micropayments and they have to provide a trade-off between efficiency and security requirements to pay low-value items. It is usual to assume low value fraud to achieve efficiency in micropayment systems. In this paper we present an improved version of an efficient and secure micropayment scheme which fulfils the security properties that guarantee no financial risk for merchants and the privacy of the customers. In addition, the proposed system defines a fair exchange between the coin and the desired good or service. In this fair exchange, the anonymity and untraceability of the customers are assured. Moreover, customers can request a refund whether they are no more interested on the services offered by merchants. As a novelty, an improvement of the scheme avoids customers to fraudulently use a refund operation to gain a little amount of money (called coupon). Thus, a new resolution subprotocol allows the merchant to avoid the loss of any single coupon.

Keywords

Micropayment, privacy, untraceability, anonymity, fairness, financial risks

INTRODUCTION

The field of electronic commerce (e-commerce) evolves day by day introducing new applications and services. One of these applications is the payment of small amounts of money to purchase low cost services or goods. This kind of payments is called micropayment and they have unique functional and security requirements inside the field of electronic payments. Here, a micropayment should offer advantages in contrast with other payment methods that tend to be costly because they are mainly designed for managing larger amounts of money. Therefore, micropayments can easily be applied to the intangible selling of goods such as information (newspapers, product reviews, location-based services, etc.), virtual gifts or electronic data (music, videos, etc). All of these examples involve low-value transactions, so the operational cost has to be as low as possible in order to be profitable for merchants and customers.

On one hand, security properties are a primary concern for the development of micropayment systems to avoid financial risks for merchants and also to ensure privacy for customers. On the other hand, efficiency and the cost for individual transactions are critical factors for the development of these systems. However, efficiency and security are usually opposed, so micropayments must provide a trade-off between these requirements.

Contribution. In (Isern-Deyà et al., 2011) we proposed a novel, efficient and secure micropayment scheme to pay low value items assuring privacy for customers. In this paper we propose an improved version of the protocol. The system uses anonymous and untraceable coins which are used in a fair exchange between customers and merchants to pay the desired good or service. The system detects and avoids double-spending and overspending, protects from forgeability and moreover allows customers to request a secure refund for partially used or unused coins.

Moreover, now the customers cannot use the refund subprotocol to fraudulently refund a single spent coupon. We have added a new resolution subprotocol that allows the merchant to deposit the received coupons even when the customers are trying to cheat, avoiding the loss of money, including very small amounts.

Organization. The work is organized as follows. First we briefly describe the features and security requirements of micropayments. Next section surveys the related work. Following section summarizes the cryptographic background used in our scheme. Then we define the micropayment protocol. In the following section we present a security overview of the protocol. Finally, the work includes the conclusions and future works.

MICROPAYMENTS SCHEMES OVERVIEW

In this section we list the involved parties and the common protocols in the micropayment model (Papaefstathiou et al., 2004; Poutanen et al., 1998; Schmidt et al., 1999). Moreover, we also enumerate and define the security requirements and functional features of an ideal micropayment system (Lipton et al., 1998; Papaefstathiou et al., 2004; Poutanen et al., 1998; Schmidt et al., 1999).

Involved Parties and Common Protocols

The typical involved parties in a micropayment scheme are:

- *Customer.* The party who wants to buy a good or service.
- *Merchant.* The party who wants to sell a good or service.
- *Broker or Bank.* The party who issues coins and manages payment accounts.

So, the common model consists of a customer who withdraws a coin from his broker account (*withdrawal* or *issuing* procedure) in order to purchase (*payment*, *spend* or *transaction* procedure) a good or electronic service (henceforth service) offered by a merchant. Finally, the merchant can request a deposit (*refund* procedure) in his broker account in exchange of a received coin from customer.

Security Requirements

An ideal micropayment system should accomplish a list of security requirements and functional features which are depicted below (Poutanen et al., 1998; Schmidt et al., 1999):

- *Privacy.* Privacy is an ideal feature for all electronic payment systems. Privacy in micropayments must take into account the following concerns:
 - *Anonymity.* Anonymity deals with the secrecy of the user identity in the system in such a way that the user is able to use the service without being identified.
 - *Unlinkability.* It is the property that considers whether different communications can be attributed to the same agent, then it concerns whether links can be established between senders of different transactions. So, linkability connects different transactions to a user, but this user remains anonymous.
 - *Untraceability.* It is defined as the indistinguishability of the past and future interactions of the identity of the user with the knowledge of the current transaction. Thus, the adversary has not to be able to identify the user. In general, untraceability implies anonymity.
- *Fair or Atomic Exchange.* Atomicity allows to logically link multiple operations so that either all of them are executed or none of them are (Tygar, 1996). So, for this kind of goods the atomic exchange of coins and services is desirable.

Functional Features

Moreover, a list of functional features related to efficiency and financial control are required for micropayment schemes (Lipton et al., 1998; Papaefstathiou et al., 2004):

- *Low Transactional Costs.* The costs of each microtransaction must be a small fraction of the amount transferred in the payment. Allowing low transactional costs requires adjustment in the following fields:
 - Number of interactions between parts during payment. On-line payments requiring the mediation of the bank are not desirable. The communication costs are lower in off-line payments.
 - Volume of information. The volume of transferred information related to the payment has to be minimized.
 - Computational costs. The use of asymmetric cryptography must be limited or amortized due to its processing time, certificate management costs and patented algorithms.
 - Storage requirements. The use of large databases must be avoided.
 - Use of coins. The security algorithms can be implemented more efficiently if the coins are built for specific services or specific providers rather than building generic coins for any purpose.
- *Lower Limit.* The lower limit for a micropayment must allow purchases of small pieces of information.
- *Financial Risks Control.* The assumed risks must be controlled even if security measures are limited in order to minimize costs.
 - *Partial Financial Risks Control.* It assumes that a micropayment system can allow the loss or theft of small amount of money.
 - *Total Financial Risks Control.* The system avoids any loss or theft of money.

As we can see, most of the functional features deal about efficiency, cost and theft minimization which are usually opposed to the security and privacy requirements like anonymity.

Summarizing, an ideal micropayment system should be secure, off-line, anonymous and untraceable, with low storage, computational and transactional costs. Moreover, the system must provide a fair exchange between the coin and the purchased service controlling the financial risks.

RELATED WORK

In this section we are going to make a brief review of the related work about micropayments. There are many micropayment proposals but none of them accomplish all of the required security properties and functional features described in section *Micropayment Schemes Overview*.

Almost all the analyzed schemes (Bayyapu et al., 2009; Buttyán, 2000; Esmaeeli et al., 2009; Nan et al., 2009; Nguyen et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2009; Zhao et al., 2009; Zongkay et al., 2005). In addition to these protocols, only one of them defines a revocation protocol that acts as a very simple refund protocol in order to return or exchange an expired coin (Wang et al., 2009). In general, micropayments are based on hash chains or multiple hash chains (Wang et al., 2009) but there are some of them that are not based on it (Wang et al., 2008). All the analyzed protocols claim the efficiency as a feature but some of them are using public key cryptography in the payment protocol (Esmaeeli et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2008; Zhao et al., 2009) which is not very good to achieve efficiency. Furthermore, these schemes are not anonymous because payment transactions are signed by customers, so merchants know their identities.

One of the main drawbacks detected in the reviewed micropayment schemes is the traceability of payments, because only two of them seem to accomplish some of the related privacy properties (anonymity, unlinkability, untraceability) (Bayyapu et al., 2009; Zhao et al., 2009). The system proposed in (Zhao et al., 2009) generates many identical pre-paid cards so that it is difficult to decide where the customer spends her money. The authors of (Bayyapu et al., 2009) use a partially blind signature in order to generate anonymous and untraceable coins.

The other security flaw detected is the lack of fairness during the payment procedure, so the customer or the merchant can cheat and gain financial advantage by misbehaving. The system proposed in (Buttyán, 2000) does not provide true fairness, but any misbehaviour becomes useless for customers and merchants using long hash chains. Nan et al. in (Nan et al., 2009) provides partial fairness using two hash chains. In (Zongkay et al., 2005) a fair system supporting the divisibility of coins is presented. However, this scheme only provides restricted anonymity and moreover (Yang et al., 2005) claims that the security of the protocol can be compromised by the collusion of merchants.

None of the cited systems fulfils the security and functional requirements described in section *Micropayment*

Schemes Overview. Therefore, new proposals are needed to achieve a micropayment scheme more secure and efficient.

In our previous work (Isern-Deyà et al., 2011) the presented system fulfils the properties of anonymity, untraceability, fairness, low transactional costs and financial risk control. However, the system cannot avoid an attack in where the customer spends a coupon and then refunds it. This attack results in the loss of a single coupon for the merchant.

In order to improve the system maintaining the original properties and achieve total risk control we present an improved protocol.

CRYPTOGRAPHIC BACKGROUND

Partially Blind Signature Schemes

A partially blind signature is related to the concept of blind signatures (Chaum, 1983) which plays a central role in cryptographic protocols where user anonymity is required, such as electronic cash or electronic voting schemes.

The partially blind signature was introduced in (Abe et al., 1996) and a formal security definition and a secure partially blind signature scheme in the oracle model were presented in (Abe et al., 2000). Partially blind signature allows the signer to introduce some common information, previously agreed between signer and requester, in the blind signature. This is a generalization of a blind signature scheme since the regular blind signature is a special case of partially blind signature where the common information is null.

There are some proposals of partially blind signatures in the bibliography using different security assumptions: (Chow et al., 2005; Okamoto, 2006; Wu et al., 2007) use bilinear maps; (Abe et al., 1996; Cao et al., 2005; Chien et al., 2001) are based on RSA; (Abe et al. 2000) is based on the discrete logarithm problem; and (Fan, 2003) is based on the quadratic residues problem.

Along this paper we use a partially blind signature presented in (Chien et al., 2001) in order to partially hide information. Moreover, we choose this scheme because it has a low computational cost and it is easy to implement on mobile devices. This scheme consists of four phases: (1) initialization, (2) requesting, (3) signing, and (4) extraction and verification.

Hash Chains

A hash chain ($\omega_N \dots \omega_0$) is defined as a set of values where each ω_i (with the exception of the value ω_N is obtained after the application of a one-way function (typically a cryptographic hash chain) over the value ω_{i+1} , i.e., $\omega_i = H(\omega_{i+1})$ for $0 \leq i \leq N - 1$. In order to initialize the hash chain, the generator picks and stores in a secret way a random seed value ω_N . Then, he applies iteratively the hash function H over it up to the value ω_0 , called root.

In order to proceed to the hash chain verification, the verifier has to know the root value ω_0 . Then, the verification of a chained element ω_i is done applying i times the hash function H over it, checking the relation $H^i(\omega_i) \stackrel{?}{=} \omega_0$.

The key feature of hash chains is that if a value ω_i is provided, it is not feasible to find another ω_j where $j > i$, such that $H^{(j-i)}(\omega_j) = \omega_i$.

MICROPAYMENT PROPOSAL

Scheme Overview

Our proposed micropayment scheme allows customers to spend in a secure and efficient way some monetary elements in exchange for any kind of low cost services. In order to improve the efficiency, as we state when we have explained *Functional Features*, the used coin is specific to pay a single merchant. Moreover, this coin is anonymous and untraceable according to the definitions listed previously in *Security Requirements*. In addition to that, payments made with different coins are unlinkable and customers can refund the partially spent coins.

The protocol involves the following three parties:

- C (*Customer*) is a user who uses a coin to obtain services or buy products offered by merchants.
- M (*Merchant*) is the party who offers services or products to customers.

- B (*Bank*) manages merchants and customers bank accounts and issues, deposits, refunds and exchanges coins.

The scheme uses the notation that can be found in Table 1. The proposal defines five mandatory protocols: *setup*, *service request*, *withdrawal*, *spend* and *deposit*) and two more protocols which are optional depending on the implementation and the use of the coins (*anonymous exchange* and *refund*).

General Used Notation	
$H(x)$	One-way collision resistant hash function
$H^i(x)$	$H()$ function applied i times
SK_A and PK_A	A 's keypair of a public key cryptosystem
$Cert_A$	Digital public key certificate of A
$S_A(x)$	A 's signature over the element x
$x \xleftarrow{R} Z_r$	Element x randomly chosen from Z_r set
$x \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$	Element x randomly chosen from Z_n^* set
K_S	Symmetric key
$E_{K_S}[x]$ and $D_{K_S}[x]$	Encryption and decryption of x using K_S
κ	Coin issued by B
(e, n)	RSA public key of B
(d, p, q)	RSA private key of B

Table 1: Notation used along the protocol description.

A coin κ is build around a partially blind signature scheme, so κ has three key parts: verifiably public data (called common data), data hidden to the signer (blind data) and the signature over both parts. On one hand, common data (see Table 2 for contents) is public and it should be agreed by the signer and the requester during the *service request protocol*. On the other hand, blind data contains some information hidden to the signer, the coin identifier (ω_{0C} , ω_{0M}). Finally, the signer signs both parts and outputs a coin made by a partially blind signature in the *withdrawal protocol*.

Common Information Contents	
s_{id}	Optional identifier of the service chosen by C
c	Number of payment coupons within a coupon chain (coin)
v	Value of each payment coupon. All coupons from a chain have the same value
τ_{exp}	Time mark that indicates when a coin is expired. It defines fixed dates in order to force that many coins expire at the same time to avoid traceability
$\Delta\tau_d$	System parameter that defines the time interval where <i>deposit</i> is allowed
$\Delta\tau_r$	System parameter that defines the time interval where <i>refund</i> and <i>anonymous exchange</i> are allowed

Table 2: Description of the parameters contained into the common information of the coin.

Then, C keeps secret a list of elements ($\omega_{2cC} \dots \omega_{0C}$) obtained by the use of the hash chain procedure. These elements are called *coupons* and they will be used to pay services to M using the *spend protocol*. The number of coupons is $2c+1$: $2c$ coupons available to use along the *spend protocol* and one more coupon called root coupon which is used to link the chained list of coupons to the partially blind signature. Regarding these $2c$ coupons, we can distinguish two types of them: *payment coupons* and *proof coupons* (Figure 1). A *payment coupon* (odd index) has monetary value and a *proof coupon* (even index) is used together with a *payment coupon* in order to validate it.

Figure 1. Coupon chain: creation and spending directions.

When M has some coupons received from C through the *spend protocol*, he can use the *deposit protocol* to request a credit in exchange of these coupons. To do so, he must prove that he knows how the other half of the coin identifier (ω_M) was made.

Finally, we have defined two optional protocols, *anonymous exchange* and *refund protocols* which can be implemented or not depending on whether they are considered necessary or not. The aim of both protocols is to provide C the ability to request a reimbursement of unused coupons.

Each protocol can only be used between defined time marks and time ranges, as we can see in Figure 2 where the timeline of coin's lifetime is depicted. These time marks are also useful from the point of view of efficiency because when a coin is expired, all parties can erase its related data. These time marks and intervals are included inside the common information of each coin (see Table 2).

Figure 2. Coin's timeline.

Setup

B should deploy a RSA key pair in order to use the partially blind signature scheme as described in (Chien et al., 2001).

C and M must setup an account and populate it with some initial balance at B . Then B links a digital certificate to an account in order to authenticate his customers in the withdrawal, deposit and refund protocols (if the latter is allowed).

Service Request Protocol

The *service request* protocol allows C to download a list of available services in M and then C can select a single service identified by a unique s_{id} . Each service is also linked to the common information containing clear data that should be agreed by the two parties. The *service request* protocol is defined as follows:

MAKEREQUEST. C initiates the protocol running the following steps:

1. C chooses a service from the downloaded list
2. $C \rightarrow B: E_{K_S}[s_{id}]$

PROCESSREQUEST. M follows the next steps:

1. picks random and secret identifier $\omega_{IM} \stackrel{R}{\leftarrow} Z_r$
2. hashes the secret identifier $\omega_{OM} \leftarrow H(\omega_{IM})$
3. builds $\Gamma = (s_{id}, 2c, v, \tau_{exp}, \Delta \tau_d, \Delta \tau_r)$ as common information of the coin
4. links and signs Γ with the hashed identifier $\omega_{OM}: S_M(\omega_{OM}, \Gamma)$
5. stores the relationship $[\Gamma, \omega_{IM}, \omega_{OM}]$ in his data store
6. $M \rightarrow C: \omega_{OM}, \Gamma, S_M(\omega_{OM}, \Gamma), Cert_M$

STORESDATA. C follows the next steps:

1. checks if Γ is correct (i.e. it has the expected parameters)
2. stores $[\Gamma, \omega_{0M}, S_M(\omega_{0M}, \Gamma)]$ in his data store

Withdrawal Protocol

The *withdrawal* protocol involves C and B and allows the former to withdraw an anonymous and untraceable coin from her account in B . On one hand, the coin is anonymous because it does not contain data about the identity of the customer although the withdrawal is an authenticated protocol. On the other hand, the coin is untraceable by B because the coin identifier $(\omega_{0C}, \omega_{0M})$ is hidden to B thanks to the use of the partially blind signature scheme. Then, when M executes the *deposit* protocol, B cannot trace the *withdrawal* procedure with the customer identity who spends the coin in M through the *spend* protocol. The withdrawal protocol is defined as follows:

REQUESTCOIN. C requests a coin:

1. picks $\omega_{MC} \xleftarrow{R} Z_r$ where $M = 2c$
2. builds the coupon chain $\omega_{iC} = H(\omega_{(i+1)C})$ with $0 \leq i \leq 2c-1$
3. joins identifiers $m = (\omega_{0C} \parallel \omega_{0M})$ to be blinded
4. extracts $\Gamma = (s_{id}, 2c, v, \tau_{exp}, \Delta\tau_d, \Delta\tau_r)$ for the current transaction
5. picks $\eta, \mu \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$
6. composes $\alpha = \eta^e H(m)(\mu^2+1) \bmod n$
7. generates the signature over (Γ, α) : $S_C(\Gamma, \alpha)$
8. $C \rightarrow B$: $(\Gamma, \alpha), S_C(\Gamma, \alpha), Cert_C$

SENDERANDOMCHALLENGE. B follows the next steps:

1. C 's account must meet (*balance* $\geq c \cdot v$), otherwise B stops
2. verifies if $\Gamma.2c, \Gamma.v$ and $\Gamma.\tau_{exp}$ are valid
3. picks $\lambda \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$
4. $B \rightarrow C$: λ

SENDCHALLENGERESPONSE. C follows the next steps:

1. picks $\rho \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$
2. computes $b = \eta \rho$
3. computes $\beta = b^e (\mu \cdot \lambda) \bmod n$. In the odd case that $\gcd(\beta, n) \neq 1$ start again because β has not modular inverse
4. $C \rightarrow B$: β

SIGNCOIN. B follows the next steps:

1. builds $\varphi = \beta^{-1} \bmod n$.
2. signs the blinded data $\gamma = H(\Gamma)^d (\alpha(\lambda^2 + 1)\beta^{-2})^{2d} \bmod n$
3. decreases C 's balance as (*balance* = *balance* - $c \cdot v$)
4. $B \rightarrow C$: (φ, γ)

UNBLINDINGCOIN. C follows the next steps to unblind and compose the coin:

1. computes $\Delta = (\mu\lambda + 1)\beta^{-1}b^e = \frac{\mu\lambda + 1}{\mu - \lambda} \bmod n$
2. builds the element $\Omega = \gamma\eta^2\rho^4 \bmod n$.
3. Δ and Ω complete the partially blind signature over blind message $m = (\omega_{0C}, \omega_{0M})$ and common data $\Gamma = (s_{id}, 2c, v, \tau_{exp}, \Delta\tau_d, \Delta\tau_r)$
4. the complete coin is composed by $\kappa = [(\Gamma, \Delta, \Omega), (\omega_{0C}, \omega_{0M})]$

Therefore, the coin is composed by a list of chained identifiers, called coupons $(\omega_{MC} \dots \omega_{0C})$, and a partially blind signature over the coin identifiers $(\omega_{0C}, \omega_{0M})$. The signature has two more parts: the common information string (Γ) and some data (Δ, Ω) to verify the signature.

The partially blind signature applied over the coin definition can be verified computing the following process:

INPUTS. The coin $\kappa = [(\Gamma, \Delta, \Omega), (\omega_{0C}, \omega_{0M})]$ and B 's public key (e, n)

CHECKCOIN. The partial blind signature is verified computing:

$$\Omega^e \stackrel{?}{=} H(\Gamma) H(\omega_{0C} \parallel \omega_{0M})^2 (\Delta^2 + 1)^2 \bmod n \quad (1)$$

Spend Protocol

The *spend* protocol is an offline protocol between C and M because B is not involved in it. C can execute the protocol while the coin is not expired, that is, while $\tau_{now} \leq \tau_{exp}$, (see Figure 2). The *spend* protocol defines a three steps fair exchange scheme between C and M where a micropayment and the desired service are exchanged. If the desired service costs more than a pair of coupons, C can send as many coupon pairs as necessary up to the required value using only one transaction. The *spend* protocol is depicted as follows:

MAKEREQUEST. C follows the next steps:

1. extracts the right K_S from her data store
2. extracts the *payment coupon* ω_{iC} and encrypts it: $m_1 = E_{K_S}[\omega_{iC}]$
3. $C \rightarrow M: m_1, \kappa$

VERIFYREQUEST. M follows the next steps:

1. decrypts the received request $D_{K_S}[m_1] = \omega_{iC}$
2. verifies that $\tau_{now} < \tau_{exp}$
3. verifies the signature of κ (as in equation (1))
4. checks reuse: if $i \leq j$ then M denies and stops the transaction. The index j points to the spent coupon pairs within the coin. This index will be updated at the end of this protocol.
5. verifies if ω_{iC} belongs κ performing $H^{(i-j)}(\omega_{iC}) \stackrel{?}{=} \omega_{jC}$
6. stores in the data store the tuple $(\kappa, \omega_{iC}, j = i)$
7. fills *res* with the desired service and encrypts it: $m_2 = E_{K_S}[res]$
8. $M \rightarrow C: m_2$

SENDPROOF. C follows the next steps:

1. decrypts $res = D_{K_S}[m_2]$
2. extracts the *proof coupon* $\omega_{(i+1)C}$
3. encrypts the *proof coupon* and the last *pay coupon* $m_3 = E_{K_S}[\omega_{(i+1)C}, \omega_{iC}]$
4. $C \rightarrow M: m_3$

VERIFYPROOF. M follows the next steps:

1. decrypts $D_{K_S}[m_3] = (\omega_{(i+1)C}, \omega_{iC})$
2. verifies if $\omega_{(i+1)C}$ belongs κ computing $H(\omega_{(i+1)C}) \stackrel{?}{=} \omega_{iC}$
3. updates the stored relation $(\kappa, \omega_{(i+1)C}, j = i + 1)$

Deposit Protocol

The *deposit* protocol allows M to deposit in his bank account the value of the received coupons from customers. M can request a deposit as many times as he wants while $0 < \tau_{now} - \tau_{exp} < \Delta \tau_d$ (see Figure 2) although he has not received the whole coupon chain. Then, B executes a list of verifications and if all of them are successful, B increases M 's balance according to the value of the received *payment coupons*. The *deposit* protocol is depicted as follows:

REQUESTDEPOSIT. M follows the next steps:

1. builds the request $r = (\kappa, \omega_{iM}, \omega_{kC}, k)$
2. encrypts the request $m_1 = E_{PK_B}[r]$
3. $M \rightarrow B: m_1, Cert_M$

DODEPOSIT. B follows the next steps:

1. decrypts the request $r = D_{SK_B}[m_1] = (\kappa, \omega_{iM}, \omega_{kC}, k)$
2. verifies the signature of κ (as in equation (1))
3. verifies if $\tau_{now} - \tau_{exp} < \Delta \tau_d$
4. checks M 's secret proof as $\omega_{0M} \stackrel{?}{=} H(\omega_{1M})$
5. checks reuse: if $k \leq j$ then M denies and stops the transaction
6. verifies if ω_{kC} belongs κ computing $H^{(k-j)}(\omega_{kC}) \stackrel{?}{=} \omega_{jC}$

7. deposits in M 's account the coupons value depending if $(k - j)$ is:

EVEN then B deposits $\frac{k-j}{2}$ coupons

ODD then B deposits $\frac{k-j-1}{2}$ coupons

Anonymous Exchange and Refund Protocols

Both *anonymous exchange* and *refund* protocols can be run by C while $\Delta\tau_d < \tau_{now} - \tau_{exp} \leq \Delta\tau_r$ (see Figure 2). On one hand, the *anonymous exchange* allows C to request B an exchange of a partially spent coin for another one without link to the previous coin. The value of the new coin is equivalent to the value of the non-spend coupons from the original coin. The complete *anonymous exchange protocol* is as follows:

REQUESTANONYMOUSEXCHANGE. C requests an anonymous exchange:

1. picks a new random chain root $\omega_{MC} \xleftarrow{R} Z_r$
2. builds the new coupon chain $\omega_{iC} = H(\omega_{(i+1)C})$ where $0 \leq i \leq M - 1$ and $M = 2c - k + 1 = 2l$
3. picks a 'fake' $\omega_{0M} \xleftarrow{R} Z_r$
4. joins identifiers $m = (\omega_{0C} \parallel \omega_{0M})$
5. composes a new $\Gamma' = (id_{fake} \parallel 2l \parallel \Gamma.v \parallel \tau_{exp} \parallel \Delta\tau_{op})$
6. extracts the old κ
7. extracts the last unused identifier ω_{kC} and the corresponding index k from old κ
8. picks two random numbers $\eta, \mu \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$
9. composes $\alpha = \eta^e H(m) (\mu^2 + 1) \bmod n$
10. $C \rightarrow B: (\Gamma', \alpha), \kappa, \omega_{kC}, k$

SENDERANDOMCHALLENGE. B follows the next steps:

1. checks if signature of κ (as in equation (1))
2. checks if ω_{kC} belongs κ computing $H^{(k-j)}(\omega_{kC}) \stackrel{?}{=} \omega_{jC}$
3. checks reuse of κ : if $k \leq j$ then denies and stops the transaction
4. checks that κ is already allowed to do an exchange $\tau_{now} \leq \Gamma.\tau_{exp} + 2\Gamma.\Delta\tau_{op}$
5. checks that the value of each new coupon is equal than each old coupon $\Gamma.v \stackrel{?}{=} \Gamma'.v$, otherwise denies
6. checks that the total number of coupons is not increased $\Gamma.2c \stackrel{?}{=} \Gamma'.(2l + k - 1)$, otherwise denies
7. picks $\lambda \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$
8. $B \rightarrow C: \lambda$

SENDCHALLENGERESPONSE. C follows the next steps:

1. picks a random $\rho \xleftarrow{R} Z_n^*$
2. computes $b = \eta \rho$
3. computes $\beta = b^e (\mu - \lambda) \bmod n$. In the odd case that $mcd(\beta, n) \neq 1$ start again because β has not modular inverse
4. $C \rightarrow B: \beta$

SIGNCOIN. B follows the next steps:

1. builds $\varphi = \beta^{-1} \bmod n$
2. builds $\gamma = H(\Gamma)^d (\alpha (\lambda^2 + 1) \beta^{-2})^{2d} \bmod n$
3. $B \rightarrow C: (\varphi, \gamma)$

UNBLINDINGCOIN. C follows the next steps:

1. computes $\Delta = (\mu\lambda + 1) \beta^{-1} b^e = \frac{\mu\lambda + 1}{\mu - \lambda} \bmod n$
2. computes $\Omega = \gamma \eta^2 \rho^4 \bmod n$
3. obtains the partial signature over blind message m and common data Γ' : $(\Gamma', \Delta, \Omega)$
4. the complete coin is: $\kappa' = [(\Gamma', \Delta, \Omega), (\omega_{0C}, \omega_{0M})]$

On the other hand, the *refund* protocol can be used by C to request B a reimbursement of an unused and expired coin or to claim a refund of a partially used coin exchanged through the *anonymous exchange* protocol.

The *refund protocol* is fully depicted as follows:

REQUESTREFUND. C follows the next steps:

1. builds the request $r = (\kappa, \omega_{iC}, i)$
2. encrypts the request $m_1 = E_{PK_B}[r]$
3. $C \rightarrow B: m_1, Cert_C$

DOREFUND. B follows the next steps:

1. decrypts the request $r = D_{SK_B}[m_1] = (\kappa, \omega_{iC}, i)$
2. verifies the signature of κ (as in equation (1))
3. verifies time $\Delta \tau_{op} < \tau_{now} - \tau_{exp} < 2\Delta \tau_{op}$
4. checks reuse: if $i \leq j$ then M denies and stops the transaction
5. verifies if ω_{kC} belongs κ computing $H^{(k-j)}(\omega_{kC}) \stackrel{?}{=} \omega_{jC}$
6. refunds in C 's account the coupons value depending if $(i - j)$

EVEN then B deposits $\frac{i-j}{2}$ coupons

ODD then B deposits $\frac{i-j-1}{2}$ coupons

The aim of executing the *anonymous exchange* protocol before a *refund* instance is to protect C from coin traceability. In fact, B could trace the identity of the customer and where she spends her coin whether M deposits and C refunds the same coin, because both protocols are authenticated.

Changes in Deposit, Anonymous Exchange and Refund Protocols

In micropayment systems, financial risks must be controlled. In this scenario it can be assumed that for each coin a single coupon could be lost or stolen. This case can be executed when a customer sends a payment coupon, receives the purchased product or service and stops the exchange. The merchant could not deposit the payment coupon without the corresponding proof coupon. This situation represents a small loss for the merchant. However, if the customer uses another payment coupon of the same coin, the merchant will know the value of the previous proof coupon (due to the properties of the hash chains). So the financial risks are controlled.

The inclusion of a refund subprotocol benefits customers allowing them to deposit unused coupons. However, the refund of coins allows customers to act fraudulently following these steps:

1. The customer sends the payment coupon to the merchant.
2. The merchant sends the product or service to the customer.
3. The customer does not send the proof coupon to the merchant. Instead, she contacts the bank to refund the remaining coupons of the coin during the refund period. The merchant is not able to deposit previously (during the deposit period) because he does not have the proof coupon of the received payment coupon.
4. The customer has stolen a coupon. All the non used coupons plus the stolen coupon are refunded.

The customer could repeat this set of steps with the first coupon of each coin to collect stolen coupons. If the *refund* operation is banned, the customer cannot try this fraudulent behaviour. Moreover, even without the *refund* subprotocol, if the customer does not send the last proof coupon of the coin, the merchant will always lose one coupon per coin although this action does not represent any gain for the customer.

In order to solve these financial risks we have improved the protocol modifying the *deposit*, the *refund* and the *anonymous exchange* subprotocols. This way, even maintaining the option of refunding coins the protocol not only controls financial risks but also achieves the property of total financial risks control defined in section *Functional Features*.

Regarding *deposit* protocol, the improvement is applied replacing step 7 of DODEPOSIT phase with the following flow:

Case1. k odd and *res* provided (M claims):

1. deposit value of $[\omega_{(k+1)C}, \omega_{jC}]$: $\left\lfloor \frac{(k+1)-j}{2} \right\rfloor$
2. store *res* for later refund procedure

Case2. k even (M does not claim):

1. deposit value of $[\omega_{kC}, \omega_{jC}]$: $\left\lfloor \frac{(k-j)}{2} \right\rfloor$

Otherwise. B denies

Now, if M sends only the payment coupon without the corresponding proof coupon (we call that M claims for a lost coupon), M must send to B the service response previously requested by C . The aim is to protect C against a possible event of connection lost between M and C during the *spend* protocol. If it happens, then B can provide C the lost service in the *refund* or *anonymous exchange* protocols.

The following code completes the step 6 of SENDRANDOMCHALLENGE in the *anonymous exchange* protocol and replaces step 6 of DOREFUND in the *refund* protocol:

Case1. j even (M has not claimed):

1. refund value of $[\omega_{kC}, \omega_{(j+1)C}]$: $\left\lfloor \frac{(k-(j+1))}{2} \right\rfloor$

Case2 j odd (M has claimed):

1. refund value of $[\omega_{kC}, \omega_{(j+2)C}]$: $\left\lfloor \frac{(k-(j+2))}{2} \right\rfloor$
2. send the lost *res* to C

We define ω_{kC} as the coupon from which C requests the refund. Generally, this coupon will be the chain's *seed coupon*. As we can see, in the first case the system refunds normally from the *seed coupon* up to the last unused coupon. In the second case, B also refunds from the *seed coupon* but only up to the last not claimed coupon pair. Thus, B does not refund the pair of coupons claimed before by M already deposited in M 's bank account.

SECURITY CONSIDERATIONS

In this section we are going to discuss the security properties of our protocol. The discussion is organized in 3 propositions that announce the security features of the scheme. Then the respective claims discuss and give arguments to the propositions. This discussion does not provide any demonstration of the security of the cryptographic primitives and does not pretend to be a formal analysis of the security of the protocol, but it gives evidences of the security properties of the protocol.

PROPOSITION 1. The proposed system preserves the customer privacy. So, the system provides anonymity to the customer in front of the merchant and it is only M-linkable and untraceable.

CLAIM 1. The system protects the identity of C when she uses the service.

PROOF. The communication between C and the B cannot be anonymous because customers have to authenticate in order to have access to their bank accounts and then they are allowed to withdraw coins to be used in the system. However, the customer C is anonymous against the provider M . C has to contact with M to use the requested service with the *spend* protocol and she spends some coupons inside a coin against the provided service. M can verify the coin and provides the service but he is not able to identify C . No information about the customer's identity is interchanged.

CLAIM 2. The provider can only link the payments made with the same coin.

PROOF. The proposed scheme is just M-linkable. The payments made with the same coin are linkable because they use the same hash chain with ω_{0C} as a seed. As far as the coin has $2c$ coupons, the provider can link the c transactions of this coin. However, M can never link payments from different coins and he is not able to link any coin to any identity. The system linkability could be controlled by the coupon chain length $M = 2c$.

CLAIM 3. The system is untraceable; it is not possible to link the identity of a customer with the service required by her.

PROOF. In spite of the customer authentication in the *withdrawal* protocol, it is impossible to link the withdrawn coin with the customer identity: that is the benefit in the usage of partially blind signatures. Thanks to this cryptographic technique, the identification string of a coin (i.e. ω_{0C}, ω_{0M}) is hidden to B . Besides, M is not able to identify C as we have said above. Thus, it is not possible to trace the role of a customer in the system proposed in the presented scheme, because for every instantiation of the role (i.e. every request of same customer) the spent coupon cannot be associated to any identity, even a collusion between B and M cannot do so. It is worthy to remark that al-

though a coin in our scheme is customer- and merchant-specific, B doesn't know the merchant a customer wishes to use the coin with. So, if the bank issues i coins for a customer, it cannot know if it have issued i coins for i merchants or for one merchant.

CLAIM 4. Customer privacy is achieved.

PROOF. The privacy of the messages exchanged between C and M is assured by the use of a shared key K_S which is only known by C and M , because this key has been exchanged securely using a key exchange protocol. M knows the data of the request of C because M must know this information in order to provide a good service. M could build a history of the requests of C , but it always will be limited by the 2c-linkability of the coupons of a single coin, but M never will be able to discover the identity of C , that is, he cannot link the profile with an identity.

RESULT OF PROPOSITION 1. According to the Claims 1, 2, 3 and 4 the identity of the customer is hidden in any transaction, so the customer privacy is preserved. We can assure that the protocol achieves the security requirements of anonymity, untraceability and it is only 2c-linkable.

PROPOSITION 2. A purchase is a particular case of fair exchange where a party sends a coin and she has to receive the good in return for this coin. The micropayment presented in this paper meets the fairness property.

CLAIM 5. In the *spend protocol*, if the parties behave correctly then the exchange is fair.

PROOF. According to the *spend flow*, described previously, the protocol is designed in such a way that, at the end of it, both parties have the desired items from the other party if they follow each protocol step. The merchant M will get the coupon pair from the customer C and the customer C will get the product for the merchant M .

CLAIM 6. If the customer C does not act in accordance with the *spend protocol* and tries to break the fairness of the exchange, the merchant M can correct the situation and he can restore the fairness using the *deposit protocol*.

PROOF. Certainly, if C does not send the *proof coupon* in the third step of the *spend protocol*, C has the desired service's response and M does not have the *proof coupon*. However, in order to repair the fairness of the purchase, the merchant M can run the *deposit protocol* within the deposit resolution period. While this protocol is running, M will send an odd i and the product to the B . The bank will store the product for the exception case explained in the next claim and then B will deposit the correct amount into the M account. Thus, the merchant is paid by the product sold and the fairness is restored.

CLAIM 7. If M maliciously does not send the service's response in the second step and tries to break the fairness of the exchange, the customer C can correct the situation and she can restore the fairness using the *refund protocol*.

PROOF. If M does not send the product in the second step of the *spend protocol*, the customer could be in an unfair situation if the merchant executes the *deposit protocol* because, as we have seen in the previous claim, M can get the rest of the coupon pair using this protocol. But, in this case and during the anonymous exchange time, the customer can run the *refund protocol*. In this situation, the bank B will execute the case 2 of the *refund flow*. In this case the value of j is odd and B can provide the product to C and it refunds the rest of the unused coin to C . So, the fairness has been restored.

RESULT OF PROPOSITION 2. According to Claims 5, 6 and 7 the proposed micropayment scheme is fair. C will send a pair coupon to M and she will receive the service response in return for that.

PROPOSITION 3. The protocol specifications assure that it not possible to commit fraud with the coins.

CLAIM 8. It is not possible to steal coins or coupons.

PROOF. Coins and coupons cannot be stolen because each coupon is protected with a secure symmetric key and they are only revealed one by one. If a theft of the whole coin happens, the attacker cannot deposit the coin without knowing the secret proof ω_{IM} , which is only known by M .

CLAIM 9. The scheme prevents from double spending.

PROOF. Both M and B maintain a tuple (i, ω_{IC}, κ) for all valid and unexpired coins. When M receives a new coupon from C in the *spend protocol*, M stores it and increases the new index. Then, M prevents a double spending if C

tries to use a coupon with an index less or equal than the index stored in the database of M . If it happens, M will deny the service to C . Although the reuse can be detected and avoided, this process does not reveal the identity of the customer.

In the *deposit* and *refund* protocols, the reuse prevention is similar, because B also maintains a list of valid and unexpired coins with the index of the last deposited coupon. The comparison between current and previous indexes allows B to prevent double spending as M does. In the *deposit* protocol the customer identification is automatic, because only the intended M is able to deposit the coin with the knowledge of his secret proof.

CLAIM 10. The system protects from forgeability.

PROOF. The coin forgery is not possible because the coin creation requires the knowledge of B 's private key. In order to build a proper coin, the signature on the blinded data is needed. To do that it is necessary to know the private parameters (d, p, q) of B . Thus, only B can build a genuine coin.

CLAIM 11. The system avoids overspending.

PROOF. When *withdrawal* protocol is executed, due to the fact that it is based on a debit system, B decreases the amount of money of C 's account. A customer cannot spend more money than the balance of his bank account.

CLAIM 12. The scheme allows C to ask for a refund.

PROOF. The definition of three temporal periods for the *spend*, *deposit* and *refund* protocols allows customers to spend partially the service packages. It also avoids C to lose unused coupons. The separation between the refund and deposit periods disallows the case where C could ask for the refund of a set of already used coupons but not yet deposited by M .

RESULT OF PROPOSITION 3. According to Claims 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 the micropayment system preserves the security of the coins: the stolen coins have no use, they are impossible to forge and the system protects from double spending and overspending. Also the unused coupons can be refunded.

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS

Table 3 shows the number of complex operations involved in each protocol of our micropayment scheme. Sometimes the number of hash operation depends on the amount of coupons involved in each protocol run. For example, $(i-j)$ in the *Spend* row of the table represents the number of coupons included in a spending operation. Analogously, $(k-j)$ in the *Deposit* row is the amount of coupons involved in a deposit transaction.

		Hash computation	Modular exponentiation	Modular multiplication	Random generation	Regular signature	Encryption/Decryption	Modular inverse
Service Request		1	0	0	1	1	1	0
Withdrawal	Customer	$M+1$	2	12	4	1	0	1
	Bank	1	2	5	1	0	0	2
Spend		$3+(i-j)$	0	5	0	0	6	0
Deposit		$3+(k-j)$	0	5	0	0	2	0
Anonymous	Customer	$M+1$	2	7	5	0	0	1
Exchange	Bank	$3+(k-j)$	2	10	0	0	0	1
Refund		$2+(k-j)$	0	5	0	0	2	0

Table 3: Computational analysis.

The computation complexity of our scheme is concentrated in the *withdrawal* and *anonymous exchange* protocols. The rest of the system doesn't have a high computational cost, especially at the customer side. For example, in the deposit and refund protocols only one encryption is performed by the customer C , the rest of the complex computations are performed by the bank B . The lightest protocol, as can be seen, is the *spend* protocol, since only hash computations and symmetric encryptions/decryptions are needed. Therefore, our protocol defines a very simple but powerful *spend* protocol, thus it can be used by any kind of mobile device although it has low resources. Moreover, it is also usable when low-cost items are purchased, because the operational costs to pay them are less than the product price.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work we have enhanced a previously proposed micropayment scheme accomplishing all the required security requirements and functional features, where the efficiency and low cost are preserved. We have included a modification to avoid a financial risk that can be arisen when the system allows executing the refund procedure. This flaw can be used by a misbehaviour customer to obtain in a fraudulent way a single service without provide the merchant all the information needed for him to execute the *deposit* protocol. The improvement consists on adding a new resolution subprotocol in the *deposit*, *anonymous exchange* and *refund* protocols avoiding this way the loss of money for the merchant. The scheme also grants customers the ability to request a refund of a partially used coin.

From the point of view of the security, as the analysis shows, the micropayment system is anonymous since the issued coin does not have any user identification and it is also untraceable thanks to the use of a partially blind signature scheme. Moreover, the protocol assures the fairness of the payment exchange since a number of coupons are exchanged for a service. If any conflicting case arises, the new resolution subprotocol acts preserving the fair exchange. Finally, the system assures that it is not possible to commit fraud with the coins. Thus, the scheme is secure against double spending, forgery and overspending so it implements the total financial risk control property.

From the point of view of functionalities, the scheme is efficient and it is suitable for the use by mobile devices because the system does not use expensive cryptography, such as public key cryptography during the payment phase, and communication and storage costs are low as the computational analysis proves. Moreover, the protocol allows customers to spend more than one coupon pair using the same transaction, improving the overall performance.

After a formal security analysis of our protocol, the future work will be focused on the scheme implementation and the performance evaluation over a mobile platform like Android or iOS in order to demonstrate that the scheme is suitable for the mobile environment. We will also evaluate the use of the Near-Field Communications (NFC) technology to accomplish the communications between the involved parties.

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